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DIFFERENCES IN SMILEY USAGE AND SENTIMENT IN REDDIT CORPORA

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ABSTRACT

What do smileys actually mean? Since people do not have an official dictionary on smileys - unlike dictionaries for words such as the Oxford dictionary or the Van Dale dictionary - they rely on their *gut* feeling or made-up conventions if they decide to use :) instead of :(. It is also reasonable to think that users learn from each other: if one uses :), it is likely that a person who first encounters that smiley will use it in future conversations as well. Also, smileys tend to be *loyally* used: one does not abandon a :) because :(is cooler or better.

In this thesis, we look at the sentiment state of corpora in which a smiley is used. We will discover if :) is really used more often in positive messages than :(. Furthermore, we take a look at a niche phenomenon in the form of the *reversed* smileys such as (: and): . Do they mean the same as their *normal* counterparts? And how popular are these smileys?

For this thesis the programming language Python was used to process the data. We cleaned the data for analysis and calculated the sentiment of our posts in Python (Rossum, 1995). We used NLTK's VADER to analyse the sentiment of hundredthousands of Reddit posts and their parent nodes. Analysing these posts gives us great insights in how people use smileys and how they communicate on Reddit.

We can conclude that our smiley types are used very differently. :) is the most popular smiley of our set, partly due to the fact that most Reddit posts we have encountered are of a positive kind. When we take a look at where people place smileys in their corpora, we see that most smiley types follow the same pattern with the big exception of): . On average, the length of posts which contain): is a lot bigger.

When drawing our interaction model for our smiley types, we can truly see that the differences between smiley types are present. Although :) and (: share the same hypothesized meaning of happiness, we can clearly see the differences between the sad :(and the nearly neutral): .

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PREFACE

It is almost two years ago when I started following courses at Information Science as part of my minor for the bachelor Information Technology at Hanze University of Applied Sciences. Afterwards, it turned out to be one of the best choices I have made in my life as I have learned so much about data science, information retrieval, statistics and the Python programming language.

I am pleased with the thesis that I can present to you now. This thesis might have started as any other thesis: just a random thought about a niche phenomenon. Writing this thesis and doing the research was a rough journey, but also a very informative and productive one. I was well prepared for writing the software, thanks to courses as Search Engines, Information Retrieval and Language Technology. Social Media prepared me for diving in the world of computer-mediated communication (although I have to confess that I completely forgot some papers concerning emotional contagion ;)). I will miss the University dearly and I hope to return in a few years to start with the master variant of Information Science.

I would like to thank my fellow board members of study association *RealTime* for granting me the opportunity to combine my board work and my research work for this thesis. It was a busy semester, but it was worth the effort. Special thanks to Gregory Mills, who is a great supervisor and always had good advice to make the thesis even better. His *deadline worries* have been proper motivation in the last few weeks of delivery. I would also like to thank Malvina Nissim for her lectures in preparation of the thesis, especially in the field of machine learning.

Last but definitely not least, I would like to thank my parents for their never-ending support and inspiration.

Leon F.A. Wetzel
Hoogezand, 21st of June 2018

1 | INTRODUCTION

Since smileys have been introduced to the world by Scott Fahlmann back in the 1980's, their meaning has varied and their popularity is increasing every day. Some smileys are more popular than others, believing that people use certain conventions or (made-up!) guidelines in using smileys. Some people use the same smileys their entire life, while others use them randomly, to tease others or to just try something else (or to impress someone else).

In this thesis, we take a look at various smiley types and discover whether or not their meaning is related to each other or if people use them very differently. We will discover which smiley types are very popular, how they are used and if they really express positivity, negativity or actually nothing. Our main research question is as follows:

Is :) used in the same way as (: and is :(used in the same way as): ?

To answer this particular question, we have to ask and answer additional research questions as well:

1. Are the differences between :) and :(the same as the differences between (: and): ?
2. Does :) mean the same as as (: and does :(mean the same as): ?
3. Are there statistically significant differences between the smiley types?

We used data from Reddit to analyse over 1.3 million messages containing smileys. Not only did we calculate sentiment scores, but we also looked at the length of posts, the position of smileys and the relationship between nodes. We performed our data processing and text cleaning in Python, as well as the sentiment analyses and retrieving the metadata. We used R for the statistical analyses, ranging from calculating distributions to creating a linear regression model for determining the interaction between smiley types.

After the introduction, we start exploring several background studies and we take a look at the history and meaning of smileys in computer-mediated communication. Then we learn more about the data we use: How did we collect it? What does our data consist of? In the chapter Method we take a look at the process of data analysis. We learn more about several used metrics and the process of data optimisation. After we have discussed our methods, we take a look at the results and after that we discuss the results. Finally, we look back at the research questions and conclude the research.

Most data analyses and data manipulation has been performed in Python and R. The source code for these projects - as well as the \LaTeX -files of the actual thesis - can be found online at <https://github.com/leonwetzell/thesis-IS> (Wetzell, 2018).

2 | BACKGROUND

In the following subsections, we explore the history of smileys, the background of the research and related work.

2.1 ORIGIN OF SMILEYS

Smileys - also known as emoticons - have been around the world since Scott Fahlman sent the first message containing a smiley on September 19th, 1982 (Fahlman, 2002). During his time at the Computer Science community at Carnegie Mellon University in Pittsburgh, Fahlman experienced that his fellow colleagues and students did not always correctly interpret the messages on the online bulletin boards of the university. Most of the posts on the boards were of a humorous kind, causing people to dismiss potentially important messages regarding campus parking or talk announcements. In order to mark unserious messages, Fahlman decided to use *joke markers*. He decided to use :-D for indicating jokes and :(for serious messages, because it was elegant and computer terminals could handle it well.

As time passed smileys evolved and Fahlman encountered smileys being used at other faculties at Carnegie Mellon and even at other universities. Examples of evolved smileys include ;-), :-D and noseless variants such as :) and :(, :(and :(, which were originally meant for indicating seriousness, became symbols for negativity, anger or frustration. Nowadays, the noseless variants are more popular than their original counterparts. The last few years saw the worldwide rise of unicode emojis, thanks to operating systems such as iOS, Windows and Android fully supporting these graphically upgraded smileys (Unicode, Inc., 2018).

2.2 SMILEYS IN COMPUTER-MEDIATED COMMUNICATION

But why are we actually using smileys? As we have read in the first paragraph of this chapter, smileys could be used to distinguish serious messages from unserious ones. In the world of computer-mediated communication (CMC), people do not have the nonverbal cues which give away things as sarcasm. A study by Andersen (1986) indicates that nonverbal cues greatly enhance interaction with teachers and the way students learn. In a comparable way, smileys and paralanguage make up for the lack of nonverbal cues in CMC (Tu, 2002).

Wolf (2000) explored the use of smileys by different genders. It turns out that, in mixed-gender newsgroups, men use smileys most often to express sarcasm or to tease. Males in the same group also used smileys to express regret and to apologise. Females in the same mixed-gender newsgroups most frequently used smileys to express humour, followed by teasing and sarcasm. This finding was striking, as smileys used to express teasing and sarcasm were rarely found in a female dominant newsgroup. Overall, females used the most smileys. This finding is partially supported by Witmer and Katzman (1997), whose research results also displayed more frequent smiley usage by women.

A study by Kramer et al. (2014) shows that emotional states can be transferred to other users through emotional contagion. This emotional contagion was shown in their results and it suggests that the emotions expressed by friends of a user, influence the mood of the user. We could argue that if a user uses certain smileys, the other user (with whom he conversates) is influenced by these smileys and could

use the same smileys in the conversation. A withdrawal effect was observed as well; those who were exposed to fewer emotional posts were less expressive in the days after exposing. This partially proved that emotional expression affects social engagement online.

2.3 MEANING OF SMILEYS

As far as smiley research in the area of this thesis goes, there are not a lot of papers to base this research upon. While there are numerous smiley dictionaries capturing the meanings of plenty of smileys (Wikipedia, 2018a; Speich, 1996), these dictionaries are mostly community-based and curated lists (unlike the Oxford Dictionaries or the Van Dale dictionary).

Of course, the true (*registered*) meaning of smileys is irrelevant and hard to capture as millions of users use them daily in very different ways. Many people can agree that :) is used in a more positive way than :((Dresner and Herring (2010) mentions that smileys do not always *convey emotion, but a rather pragmatic meaning*. Smileys such as ;-p and ;-)) are hard to associate with a solid-shaped emotion. Comparably, joking can be done when one is happy or sad (whereas joking is actually regarded as a type of illocutionary force¹). Being funny on the other hand can be described as a perlocutionary force². A performance of utterance with phonetic, semantic and syntactic features is regarded as a locutionary act (e.g. "Eat vegetables every day"). The example counts as a form of advice, which is an illocutionary act (Austin, 1975).

¹ Something that someone does by what he says

² For example: in order to be funny, the audience should find the utterance funny instead of the speaker himself. Another example of a perlocutionary force is the act of persuading.

3 | DATA AND MATERIAL

In this chapter, we explore more about the data and how it was collected. Furthermore, we take a look at how we will use the data and how we will prepare it for processing.

3.1 A BRIEF INTRODUCTION TO REDDIT

This thesis is centered around data from Reddit. Reddit is a website where users can share links, post comments, create new threads and upvote or downvote submissions. The website consists of so-called subreddits, which are communities centered around a particular topic, person or event (O’Gara and Garcia, 2017). Popular subreddits are currently soccer, politics, funny, movies and AskReddit (Baumgartner, 2018b). It is at the subreddits where people make submissions, where other users can make comments and/or make new posts.

Figure 1: Example of a submission on Reddit.

Reddit is constructed as a tree. Submissions are connected to subreddits and comments are part of a submission. A comment can be placed as a reaction to the submission or as a reaction to another comment. This makes discussions somewhat summarized and it is very easy to react to specific comments. Below we can see an example of a comment on a submission regarding the latest developments in the 2018 FIFA World Cup Russia. The comment has several *children* comments as well.

Figure 2: Example of a comment structure on Reddit.

3.2 PUSHSHIFT.IO

pushshift.io is a website maintained by Jason Baumgartner, where visitors can read articles about data science and social media ingest and analytics. It also hosts Reddit data collected by Baumgartner on files.pushshift.io. Since Baumgartner shared his data on Reddit, the popularity grew quickly. Several research papers have used Baumgartner's data (including this thesis of course!) (Baumgartner, 2018a).

We have downloaded 77.476.580 posts from pushshift.io. These Reddit posts were made between December 2005 and December 2010. Our posts originate from 4472 different subreddits. The data has been collected since the summer of 2014 by Baumgartner. When it comes to file sizes, our downloaded data is more than 42 gigabytes big. As one can see in table 1, the amount of posts per year grew quickly.

Year	Amount of Reddit posts
2005	1.075
2006	417.184
2007	2.463.559
2008	7.242.871
2009	18.862.834
2010	48.489.057
Total	77.476.580

Table 1: Distribution of Reddit posts per year from pushshift.io (where 2005 only has posts from December).

3.3 PRAW

The Python Reddit API Wrapper - also known as PRAW - is a Python package that allows for simple access to Reddit's API (Boe, 2018). PRAW is currently maintained by Bryce Boe. The project started in August 2010 by Timothy Mellor.

PRAW can be used to retrieve account information, comments, submissions and entire subreddits. PRAW can be used in addition to the Reddit posts we have collected through pushshift.io. This is especially useful for retrieving information that is not available through the data from pushshift.io. For example, we could retrieve user information and link that to our Reddit corpora.

3.4 FILTERING

Relevant Reddit posts are posts which contain (at least) one smiley. The smileys we are interested in are `:`, `:(`, `(:` and `):`. To check a Reddit post for any smiley presence, we run the Python code below for the entire dataset (in other words: all JSON-files containing the Reddit posts).

```

1 import glob
2 import json
3 smileys = {':', ':(', '(:', ':)'}
4
5
6 def main():
7     for filename in glob.glob('*.json'):
8         with open(filename) as f:
9             for line in f:
10                dat = json.loads(line)
11                if any(smiley in dat['body'] for smiley in smileys):
12                    print(json.dumps(dat))

```

The generated output is gathered into a new JSON-file which forms our new primary dataset. Filtering by smileys returned us 1.338.815 Reddit posts, which is just a fraction (nearly 2%) of the entire dataset we have downloaded!

Although the *smiley* dataset is our primary dataset, we will not dispose the already downloaded data. We will use the other Reddit posts to link nodes to each other (creating parent-node relationships). This will be further explained in the next chapter.

3.5 JSON OBJECTS

[pushshift.io](#)'s data consists of millions of lines of JSON, with each line representing one Reddit post. A line is made up of eighteen key/value pairs, which can be seen below.

```
1 {
2   "subreddit": "reddit.com",
3   "score": 3,
4   "ups": 3,
5   "author_flair_css_class": null,
6   "created_utc": 1167609605,
7   "body": "In the city I live in, I probably am. :(",
8   "controversiality": 0,
9   "subreddit_id": "t5_6",
10  "link_id": "t3_wiw8",
11  "stickied": false,
12  "gilded": 0,
13  "distinguished": null,
14  "retrieved_on": 1473809765,
15  "author": "almkglor",
16  "author_flair_text": null,
17  "id": "cw13r",
18  "edited": false,
19  "parent_id": "t1_cwjuc"
20 }
```

For this thesis, we mainly focus on the body of a post. Furthermore, we also need the ID, the parent ID, the link ID, the creation date, the collection date and the subreddit and its ID.

Although the other features are interesting and nice to have as well, they do not fall in the scope of this thesis. Integrating author information is a study itself and it could provide useful information about user behaviour.

4 | METHOD

The following subsections explain the process of data preparation, retrieving smileys, retrieving parent nodes, retrieving the length of Reddit posts, calculating sentiment and calculating the interaction between smiley types.

4.1 PREPARING FOR ANALYSIS

In this section, we cover the preparation steps. As we retrieve the raw Reddit posts from pushshift.io, we need to optimise them in order to properly use them.

4.1.1 Retrieving smiley types

We have initially filtered our data by smiley presence, but we have not retrieved those smileys, nor do we know which smiley type is present in the post. Once again, we run a Python script to retrieve the smiley type per line and to add that smiley to the line of JSON for further use.

```
1 import json
2 smileys = {':)', ':(', ':(', '):'}
3
4
5 def main():
6     with open('filtered', 'r') as f:
7         for line in f:
8             dat = json.loads(line)
9             for smiley in smileys:
10                if smiley in dat['body']:
11                    dat['smiley'] = smiley
12                    print(json.dumps(dat))
13                    break
```

The code snippet above returns us a new JSON file containing the smileys which we have found per line. In figure 3 and table 5 we can see that the distribution is extremely positively skewed towards the normal happy smiley :).

Figure 3: Distribution of smiley types across the Reddit posts.

(:):	:(:)
6.906	102.653	321.721	907.532

Table 2: Distribution of Reddit posts per smiley type.

4.1.2 Linking nodes

As mentioned in chapter 3, Reddit is constructed as a tree. We can assume that the Reddit posts are interconnected, meaning that a post can be a reaction to a submission or a post is a comment on another comment. Every post - which we can also call node - has a parent node. This parent node can be a submission or another node. In this subsection, we will take a look at connecting nodes with parent nodes.

We are interested in the parent ID's of the Reddit posts we have collected in the first paragraph of this chapter. We collect these parent ID's, strip the first three characters, add them to a set and put them in a Python pickle¹. We use this pickle in another application which links the parent ID's with their respective body. In this Python application, we use the entire downloaded dataset from pushshift.io to link a node body with a parent ID.

Linking nodes was a tricky act to do. Our dataset contains very old nodes which are more often than not *orphaned*: the parent nodes are either removed or archived by Reddit. PRAW is a powerful tool to both extract comments or submission titles, but it is rather slow as we have to request a lot of data. Although PRAW works with lazy objects², we have to wait too long to get all the data we need. Instead, we prefer to skip retrieving Reddit data through PRAW as a minority of the posts does not have parent information.

4.1.3 Converting date and time

The data from pushshift.io contains a *created* datetime and a *retrieved* datetime in UNIX time, also known as epoch time. The UNIX Epoch started its count on the 1st of January, 1970 ([Wikipedia, 2018b](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Unix_time)). As part of our data preparation, we convert these times to 'human' times and dates using build-in Python functionality.

4.1.4 Adding other metadata and text cleaning

Other useful metrics we can apply for our data analysis are the length of posts and the position of smileys within a post. We determine these metrics for both parent nodes as the nodes from our smiley dataset. We do not assume that parent nodes contain smileys, so therefore we only save the smiley metrics of the node.

We use NLTK to tokenise our posts and to extract only the useful parts of text we can analyse. We use NLTK's TweetTokenizer to tokenise our posts. The TweetTokenizer performs better tokenisation than NLTK's original tokeniser, as it is optimised for use on social media platforms and it is able to properly tokenise our smileys ([Loper and Bird, 2002](https://lernerandbird.com)). We also remove stop words from the posts. We could also lowercase posts and remove punctuation, but this harms the functionality of the sentiment classifier. More on sentiment analysis will be covered in section 4.4.

¹ Pickle can be used to serialize or de-serialize Python object structures.

² A lazy object only contains useful data when the object is used by the application.

4.2 POST LENGTHS

While we are cleaning our text as mentioned in the previous subsection, we also retrieve the length of a post and the position of the smiley within the post. The length of a post is measured in tokens.

Figure 4: Length of nodes and parent nodes.

	Minimum	1st. Quartile	Median	Mean	3rd. Quartile	Maximum
Nodes	1.00	12.00	25.00	60.77	61.00	5799.00
Parent nodes	1.00	18.00	37.00	72.43	79.00	5552.00

Table 3: Distribution of Reddit posts per smiley type.

In figure 4 we are not displaying the outliers. We can see that most posts contain less than 150 tokens. When we take the statistics into account, we can see that, on average, a node contains almost 61 tokens.

Not all parent nodes could be found (i.e. a node is removed or could simply not be retrieved). We assigned the value 0 to those nodes. In table 5, we have removed these posts to show usable statistics. Parent nodes are on average larger than nodes.

Figure 5: Lengths of posts per smiley type.

In figure 5 - of which we removed the outliers for displaying purposes - we can see that `);` has larger post lengths in comparison with the other smiley types. It is also worth mentioning that `:)` and its *brother-type* `(:` share nearly identical distribution.

	Minimum	1st. Quartile	Median	Mean	3rd. Quartile	Maximum
All nodes	1.00	12.00	25.00	60.77	61.00	5799.00
<code>:)</code>	1.00	11.00	25.00	54.85	57.00	2957.00
<code>(:</code>	1.00	9.00	21.00	56.56	56.00	1871.00
<code>:(</code>	1.00	10.00	19.00	36.59	39.00	5799.00
<code>);</code>	1.00	54.00	115.00	189.20	231.00	5023.00

Table 4: Distribution of Reddit posts per smiley type.

4.3 SMILEY POSITION RATIO

As mentioned in subsection 4.1.4, we have retrieved post lengths and the positions of smileys in the nodes. We use both metrics to calculate the Smiley Position Ratio (SPR). For calculating the SPR, we apply the following formula:

$$SPR = \frac{LT}{SP} \quad (1)$$

In formula 1, LT stands for the length of a text and SP is the position of a smiley within a text. The SPR is a weighted position of a smiley in a given amount of text. If the SPR equals 0, it means that a smiley can be found at the beginning of a text. If the SPR equals 1, a smiley can be found at the end of a text.

	Minimum	1st. Quartile	Median	Mean	3rd. Quartile	Maximum
All nodes	0.00	0.6959	1.00	0.8170	1.00	1.00
<code>:)</code>	0.00	0.8592	1.00	0.8497	1.00	1.00
<code>(:</code>	0.00	0.7205	1.00	0.8281	1.00	1.00
<code>:(</code>	0.00	0.8667	1.00	0.8513	1.00	1.00
<code>);</code>	0.00	0.1667	0.3556	0.4195	0.6406	1.00

Table 5: Stastical metrics for the SPR per smiley type.

We can see in table 5 and figure 6 that most posts end with a smiley. A major exception to this rule is `);`, which behaves very differently in comparison to the other smiley types.

4.4 SENTIMENT ANALYSIS

Calculating sentiment is one of the steps we take to check the meaning of our various smiley types. We calculate sentiment of our preprocessed parent nodes and our preprocessed nodes. The preprocessing is described in subsection 4.1.4.

Sentiment analysis is the treatment of opinion, sentiment and objectivity in text. Sentiment analysis can be done over an entire corpus or single sentences, leading to different scores and thus causing difficulties. Over the years, sentiment analysis has been improved greatly. Since the start of the 21st century the amount of research papers grew quickly (Pang et al., 2008).

Figure 6: Length of nodes and parent nodes.

4.4.1 Introduction to VADER

Once again, we use a feature of NLTK to help us. We use NLTK's VADER (which is short for Valence Aware Dictionary and sEntiment Reasoner) to calculate various scores per class of sentiment. A class of sentiment can be positive, negative, neutral or compound (which is an aggregated score of the first three classes) (Hutto and Gilbert, 2014). VADER takes a string as input and returns a Python dictionary containing the four sentiment classes as keys and the calculated scores as values.

So, how does VADER work internally? VADER heavily depends on lexicons of sentiment-related words. Every word in the lexicon is rated either negatively or positively, as well as to which extent it is negative or positive. These words are rated manually; human annotators - part of Amazon's Mechanical Turk - did the rating for the lexicon (Rachiele, 2017).

The journey is good and the boat is nice.

The sentence above contains two words in the lexicon (which are **good** and **nice**). These words have high positive ratings. Based on these values, VADER calculates the four sentiment classes. The first three classes have an accumulated value of 1. The compound value is computed **before** the calculation of the scores of neg, neu and pos. The compound score is a normalised score of the sum of scores using an alpha value.

Last but not least, VADER also takes punctuation and capitalization into account. This is very important to take into consideration when implementing the test software and when performing preprocessing.

4.4.2 Nodes

First we analyse the sentiment of our nodes. Not only do we calculate the sentiment classes, but we assign a label - pos, neg or neu - as well. This makes it easier for us to construct histograms and to do quick interpretations. Labels also help us tackle an issue we encountered, which will be explained in the next paragraph.

In figure 7 and table 7 we can see that the majority of posts is positive. Initial calculations have proven that there were more neutral posts, which is courtesy of

Figure 7: Amount of Reddit posts per sentiment label.

	Minimum	1st. Quartile	Median	Mean	3rd. Quartile	Maximum
All labels	-1.00	-0.1260	0.5267	0.3442	0.8172	1.00

Table 6: Statistical metrics for the compound scores (all labels).

the *lexicon theory* we discussed in the last paragraph. Most sentences contain words that are not (really) positive or negative. If we look at the example from the last paragraph (*The journey is good and the boat is nice*), we can see that there are no more *influencing* words other than **good** and **nice**.

To solve this matter, we use the compound scores and assign a label based on the compound score. If the compound score is larger than 0.2 ($C > 0.2$), we assign the label **pos**. If the compound score is less than -0.2 ($C < -0.2$), we assign the label **neg**. Anything in between -0.2 and 0.2 ($-0.2 < C < 0.2$) will get the label **neu**.

neg	neu	pos
314.308	103.700	920.807

Table 7: Distribution of sentiment labels of nodes.

4.4.3 Parent nodes

Just as the nodes, we first analyse the sentiment of the parent nodes. We use the filtered posts - which do not have a length of 0 - to check the distribution of labels. As we can see in figure 8 and table 8, the distribution of sentiment labels of the parent nodes looks similar to the distribution of sentiment labels of our nodes.

neg	neu	pos
188.846	67.737	449.188

Table 8: Distribution of sentiment labels of parent nodes.

Figure 8: Amount of filtered parent posts per sentiment label.

5 | RESULTS

In this chapter, we finally see the results of our analyses and we put our well-prepared data to the test. We perform our statistical analyses in R (R Core Team, 2018).

5.1 STATISTICS, STATISTICS, STATISTICS...

We perform a few statistical tests to check if the differences between smiley types are significant and thus not depending on luck or chance. We might encounter that there might be no differences at all, of course.

5.1.1 Relation between parent sentiment and node sentiment

We would like to know if there is a relation between the compound scores of parent nodes and the nodes. In other words, we want to see if both variables are independent of each other. We form the following hypotheses:

H_0 : There is a relation between parent sentiment and node sentiment.

H_a : There is no relation between parent sentiment and node sentiment.

We want to use Pearson's correlation coefficient r to quantify the relationship between the two variables. Our alpha value ($= \alpha$) is 0.05. The degrees of freedom ($df = N - 1$) are 705770. We also want to see if there is a relationship, so we take a look at our scatter plot.

Figure 9: Parent node sentiment by node sentiment.

We cannot make much sense of the scatter plot, so therefore we perform our analysis in R.

```

1 ##
2 ## Pearson's product-moment correlation
3 ##
4 ## data: filtered_posts$node_sent_comp and filtered_posts$parent_sent_comp
5 ## t = 192.76, df = 705770, p-value < 2.2e-16
6 ## alternative hypothesis: true correlation is not equal to 0
7 ## 95 percent confidence interval:
8 ## 0.2214219 0.2258546
9 ## sample estimates:
10 ## cor
11 ## 0.2236394

```

We tested whether parent sentiment and node sentiment were related (with $\alpha = 0.05$). Our hypotheses were H_0 : parent sentiment and node sentiment are independent, and H_a : parent sentiment and node sentiment are dependent. In our sample of filtered Reddit posts (with $N = 705771$), which all have parent nodes, we obtained the sentiment of the nodes and the sentiment of their parent nodes. There is a positive correlation between the two variables ($r = 0.2236394$, $df = 705770$, $p < 2.2e-16$). Since $p < \alpha$, we can reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis **that there is a relation between parent sentiment and node sentiment**.

5.1.2 Difference between parent node and node post lengths

We would like to know if there is a significant difference between the length of parent nodes and the length of a node. Although we have drawn a boxplot (figure 4 and table 5) to check this, we want to perform the independent samples t-test - also known as Welch Two Sample t-test - to check if the average parent node length is larger than the node length. We fulfil to all assumptions the t-test has. The hypotheses are as follows (with p for parent node and n for node):

$$H_0: \mu_p = \mu_n$$

$$H_a: \mu_p > \mu_n$$

We use $\alpha = 0.05$. The mean parent node length is 72.43 and the mean node length is 60.77. We perform the t-test on nodes which have a parent node.

```

1 ##
2 ## Welch Two Sample t-test
3 ##
4 ## data: filtered_posts$parent_length and filtered_posts$node_token_length
5 ## t = 41.393, df = 1410300, p-value < 2.2e-16
6 ## alternative hypothesis: true difference in means is greater than 0
7 ## 95 percent confidence interval:
8 ## 7.952168 Inf
9 ## sample estimates:
10 ## mean of x mean of y
11 ## 72.43083 64.14958

```

We tested whether the average length of parent nodes is significantly higher than the average length of nodes. Our hypotheses were: $H_0: \mu_p = \mu_n$ and $H_a: \mu_p > \mu_n$. We conducted an independent samples t-test, because the samples were independent and σ was unknown. The mean parent node length is 72.43 and the mean node length is 64.15. The effect size was very small (Cohen's $D = 0.0696796$) and it reached significance at α -level 0.05: $t(1410300) = 41.393$, $p < 2.2e-16$. We can reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis that the length of parent nodes is higher than the nodes.

5.2 PROPORTIONS

Smiley usage develops over time and follows certain trends and influences. Some smileys or internet trends are popular in one year and forgotten in the other year. To check if this phenomenon occurs in the smiley world as well, we take a look at the relative proportions over the years.

5.2.1 Yearly overview of posts

Let's take a look at the distribution of posts over the years.

Figure 10: Distribution of smileys over the years.

Although our dataset should consist of posts between December 2005 and December 2010, our dataset contains posts from the 1st of January 2011. This probably has to do with time zones, but it does not influence our analysis much. We will also take a look at the smiley distributions over the years. We can see that smileys do not vanish: people keep using them regardless of increasing/decreasing popularity.

	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011
(:	0	61	185	425	1360	4875	3
):	4	1393	5063	10987	26696	58501	9
:(1	687	4453	18284	70168	228084	44
:)	12	4860	22056	53857	195301	631317	129

Table 9: Distribution of smileys over the years

5.2.2 Comparing smiley normality proportions

We regard :) and :(as normal smileys; these smileys are conventional and are used most often of all the smiley types and the meaning they represent. The abnormal smileys - sometimes referred to as weird smileys - are (: and):. These smileys are less used than their *reversed* counterparts. In this subsection, we compare the proportions between the normal and abnormal smiley types.

	Normal	Weird
Absolute	1229253	109562
Relative	0.91816494	0.08183506

Table 10: Amount of Reddit posts per level of normalness.

Figure 11: Comparison of normalness of smileys.

5.2.3 Comparing smiley happiness proportions

We talk about happy smileys when we mean :) and (;, as most people use them to express happiness and the fact that they look happy. We think of unhappy smileys when we see :(and);, as most people use them to express unhappiness.

Figure 12: Comparison of normalness of smileys.

	Happy	Unhappy
Absolute	914441	424374
Relative	0.6830227	0.3169773

Table 11: Amount of Reddit posts per level of happiness.

5.3 INTERACTIONS

We can display our array of smiley types in table 12, with regards to the last paragraphs. We call this table the Smiley Type Matrix (STM).

	Normal	Abnormal
Happy	:)	(:
Unhappy	:():

Table 12: Smiley Type Matrix

This matrix displays the relationships between the smiley types. To put the contents of the matrix to the test, we create a linear regression model. As the response variable, we select the compound score we presented in subsection 4.4 as our dependent/predicted variable. Our independent/predictor variables are the normalness (which is called *conventional* in our model) and the happiness (which is called *smiley_type* in our model). We let R do the calculations and it creates our model. So, what are the results? R returns us the output below. In addition that output, we can also use the interaction plot shown in figure 13.

```

1 ##
2 ## Call:
3 ## lm(formula = node_sent_comp ~ smiley_type * conventional, data = dat)
4 ##
5 ## Residuals:
6 ##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
7 ## -1.62343 -0.18090  0.07498  0.27418  1.25920
8 ##
9 ## Coefficients:
10 ##                                Estimate Std. Error t value
11 ## (Intercept)                    0.5955197  0.0004686 1270.926
12 ## smiley_typeUnhappy              -0.8550179  0.0009159 -933.509
13 ## conventionalWeird               0.0289150  0.0053907   5.364
14 ## smiley_typeUnhappy:conventionalWeird 0.2266907  0.0056232  40.314
15 ##                                Pr(>|t|)
16 ## (Intercept)                    < 2e-16 ***
17 ## smiley_typeUnhappy              < 2e-16 ***
18 ## conventionalWeird               8.15e-08 ***
19 ## smiley_typeUnhappy:conventionalWeird < 2e-16 ***
20 ## ---
21 ## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
22 ##
23 ## Residual standard error: 0.4464 on 1338811 degrees of freedom
24 ## Multiple R-squared:  0.4128, Adjusted R-squared:  0.4128
25 ## F-statistic: 3.138e+05 on 3 and 1338811 DF,  p-value: < 2.2e-16

```

A normal happy smiley :) has a mean sentiment score of 0.5955197. If we look at its unhappy counterpart :(, we can see that it has a mean sentiment score which is around 0.86 below the mean sentiment score of the normal happy smiley (which is equal to almost -0.26).

Now, we can also see that use of (: leads to slightly higher sentiment scores (estimated at a raise of 0.0289150 in comparison with the normal happy smiley). When we look at);, we see that there is a raise of almost 0.2266907 from the mean sentiment score of :(. This puts); in the neutral zone: posts which are almost perfectly neutral of kind.

Figure 13: Visualised interaction between smiley types.

6

DISCUSSION & CONCLUSION

This thesis has performed an extensive investigation into the use of various smiley types in computer-mediated communication. Reddit has proven to be a positive and conventional playground of common smiley types between 2005 and 2011. We have analysed over 705771 Reddit posts, performing not only sentiment analyses but so much more. We took the length of posts into account, as well as information about parent nodes and the actual position of smileys within posts.

If we take a look back at our research questions, we can complement them with a proper answer.

1. *Are the differences between :) and :(the same as the differences between :(and): ?*
The differences are not the same between the smiley types and their type-equivalents. We have seen that not only the proportions of usage are different, their sentiment context is completely different.
2. *Does :) mean the same as :(and does :(mean the same as): ?*
The interaction plot shows us that): is used in a more neutral context than its assumed equivalent :(. We have also seen that): is used in very different positions within corpora in comparison with the other smiley types. We can confirm that at least :(and): do not mean the same. We can also confirm that the differences between :) and :(have proven to be negligible, as they shared nearly similar distributions and their mean sentiment scores were almost equal. We can accept that :) and :(mean the very same. However, we do not know why one prefers a smiley above the other one¹ or).
3. *Are there statistically significant differences between the smiley types?*
Our regression model shows that the differences in sentiment scores between :(and): are significant. Furthermore, the proportions in usage can be called significant as well since there are huge differences between *normal* smileys and *weird* smileys (as shown in figure 11 and figure 12).

Last but not least, we have our main research question:

Is :) used in the same way as :(and is :(used in the same way as): ?

As mentioned in the other research questions, we have discovered that): is used in more neutral context than all the other smiley types. :) and :(share identical traits and tend to be used in the same way. Their sentiment scores are nearly identical and the positions of these smileys in corpora are matching. :) and :(are used in the same way, whereas :(and): are not used in the same way.

We can conclude that when it comes to happiness, the smileys :) and :(do actually not differ both in meaning and usage. It was interesting to see that the negative smileys are different; not only does): completely break the rule of most smiley types being present at the end of a text, but the context in which): is used is nearly neutral when compared to :(. This has shown that): is used in less expressive posts where emotion is less a factor than normal posts.

Although we have proven that there are numerous differences between smileys and their usages, we may need more information about the authors who use them every day in computer-mediated communication. There is much to learn about how

¹ It is suggested by belief that the smiley choice has to do with handedness, where right-handed persons use :) or :(and left-handed persons use (:

a person not only uses smileys, but also in which context and if their way of using smileys evolves or dissolves. This requires much more information and research data from Reddit, which does not lie within the scope of this very thesis.

Quite often have we experienced that the lack of computing power and computing time has slightly hindered us. The Reddit API changed when we were working on this thesis (presumably courtesy of *New Reddit*²), causing even more hinder. It also limits us, as we cannot request a lot of information in a small amount of time. If we want to look further than this thesis and do more analyses over an even bigger data set, we need to scale up and simply have time to process (something students never have, of course).

Let's not forget that we have performed extensive research on a real-life dataset, containing actual and representative data about how people communicate and use smileys in computer-mediated communication. When we started, we had to depend on gut feeling and assumptions of modern culture. As people do more research on the smiley phenomenon, we get closer to that smiley dictionary we talked about so many times in this thesis. But is that actually something we want and need, as smileys are so diverse and quickly evolving?

² Reddit rolled out its redesign throughout 2018

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